

Practical Ways to Optimize Costs in Cloud Platforms

Author 1: Rohan Maruti Kolwale

Author 2: Mr. Arun Udayasuriyan

Student of BCA(Hons.)-AI/ML, Parul University,

Enrollment no:-2405101270114,

Mail id:-2405101270114@paruluniversity.ac.in

ABSTRACT

As the technologies are Growing with time the Cloud Platforms emerged and Moving to the Cloud is very popular for businesses this days as it is very flexible way and easy to scale up. Cloud Platforms like Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud Platform (GCP) charges for everything we use and small cost add's up fast. Many Companies get shock when they see their monthly bills. This Research Paper looks at Problem of wasted spending in cloud. It explains the simple, practical strategies and ways that anyone can use to lower their cloud bills without affecting the performance. We will look at several methods like Managing storage in better ways, picking right server size, and many other things. The goal is to show that saving money in cloud is not magic ,it just requires paying attention and using the right tools.

Keywords:Cost-Optimization,Cloud-Platforms,Efficient-Usage.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last ten years the concept of cloud is trending , the way companies build the software has changed completely [1] "Market-Oriented Cloud Computing: Vision, Hype, and Reality for Delivering IT Services as Computing Utilities". Instead of buying expensive physical server's ('on-premises'), company started renting compute powers from cloud providers like AWS, Azure and Google Cloud [2] "Efficient Resource Management for Cloud Computing Environments". This is Cloud Computing [3] "Cost-Aware Resource Allocation for Cloud Computing".

The biggest benefit of Cloud is "pay-as-you-go" model, which means pay only for what you use [4] "A Survey on Cloud Resource Allocation and Cost Optimization Techniques". It turns the big costs into small costs [5] "Energy and Cost-Aware Scheduling of Virtual Machines in Cloud Data Centers".

But the problem is: It is very easy to spin up new resources [6] "Dynamic Resource Provisioning for Cloud Computing: A Cost Optimization Approach". Developers might turn on powerful machines or Servers for test and forget to turn it off for weeks or a company might rent a big Server when a tiny one would do the job Because the bill only comes once a month or years these mistakes aren't noticed

immediately [7] "An Efficient Cost Optimization Approach for Cloud Computing Services".

Many studies show that huge percentage of cloud spending is actually wasted money [4] "A Survey on Cloud Resource Allocation and Cost Optimization Techniques". This paper will explain why these costs get out of control and also list out the ways to optimize this costs [3] "Cost-Aware Resource Allocation for Cloud Computing". We want to get best performance for the lowest prices [5] "Energy and Cost-Aware Scheduling of Virtual Machines in Cloud Data Centers".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Before looking to solutions ,it is important to see the current situation in industry. I studied several reports and articles to understand why cloud costs are such a big issue right now.

According to "State of the Cloud Report" by Flexera(2023), cost management is the biggest challenge for organizations from many years in a row. The report found that companies estimate they waste about 32% of their cloud budget. This means for every \$100 they Spend \$32 is thrown away on things they don't need.

Other researches like Gartner, have pointed out that main cause of this waste is "oversizing". This confirms

that people often choose servers that are too powerful for their actual needs just to be safe.

I also looked at documentation from Amazon web Services(AWS) and Microsoft Azure. Both companies admits that customers struggle with complex pricing models. They suggest that “pay-as-you-go” model which provides flexibility requires strict discipline. The literature clearly shows that technology is not the problem ,the problem is how humans manage the resources.

Cloud Computing Global Market Report 2025

Top cloud challenges

flexera All=753, Enterprise: N=621, SMB: N=132
Source: Flexera 2024 State of the Cloud Report

III. Understanding the Cloud Cost -Problem

Why do cloud bills get so high ? The main reason is that cloud is little much complex. There are thousands of different services and each has its own price tag. It's not just about creating Virtual Instances (virtual Computer). You also pay for the data which goes in and out of computer and the hard drive attached to it (storage).

A common issue is “Over-Provisioning”, which means renting bigger then you need let us take an example: It's like renting a big truck to transport a single chair. You are paying for empty space.

Another issue is “Zombie infrastructure”. These are resources that were turned on but aren't being use anymore. They are not being used anymore but still increasing the cost every hour.

Below is general idea of How cloud spending is going to grow globally, it shows why this is a big topic right now:

IV. Key Strategies for Cost Optimization(Methods)

Fixing Cloud costs doesn't mean you have to stop building the things. It means being smarter about how you build them.The most common and effective ways to save money are:

5.1 Right-Sizing :

It is the most basic step.It means matching your server size to your actual workload.

Cloud Providers offer's hundreds of types of virtual machines.Some have lots of CPU Power, some have huge amount of RAM, and some are balanced. If you are choosing Virtual Machine that has 64GB RAM but you just requires 8GB , then you are wasting enormous amounts of money.

To fix these you have to look at “utilization metrics”.These are graphs that show how hard your server is working. If CPU is running at only 5% usage for whole month, that server is too big and You have to Switch it to smaller type. It is a continuous process because application needs change over time.

You see utilization metrices in Cloud through Amazon CloudWatch, Azure Monitor, and Google Cloud Monitoring.

5.2 Using Savings Plans and Reserved Instances(RIs) :

The Standard way to pay for cloud is 'On-Demand'. This is one of the most flexible option but also the most expensive. It's like buying a single train ticket every time you travel.

If you know you will need server for long time (like a year or three years), you should not use On-Demand. Instead, use Reserved Instances (RIs) or Savings Plans.

Think of this like buying a yearly train pass. Because you commit to pay for whole year or three years upfront, the cloud provider gives you massive discount sometimes up to 70% off the regular price. This is one of the best way to save lots of money.

5.3 Utilizing Spot Instances for Flexible Jobs :

Sometimes the cloud providers have extra server capacity that nobody is using at moment. They sell this spare capacity at cheap prices(low), sometimes even 90% cheaper than usual prices.

These are called "Spot Instances" (on AWS and Azure) or "Preemptible VMs" (on Google Cloud).

The problem with "Spot Instances" is that the provider can take these servers back with very little warning time (2-minutes notification) if someone else is willing to pay full price for them.

Therefore you cannot run your main website or Database on Spot Instances. If they get turned off, your site goes down. Spot Instances are perfect for testing, or processing large batches of data.

5.4 Storage Optimization :

Storing terabytes of data on high-speed hard drives is expensive.

Cloud Platform's offer different "tiers" of storage:

- Hot Storage: Fast, expensive, meant for data you use every day.
- Cold Storage: Slower, much cheaper (low cost), meant for backups or data you touch once a month.
- Archive Storage: Extremely Cheap, but it takes hour to get your data back.

A good Strategy is to use "Lifecycle Policies". These are the automatic rules. For example: You can set a rule that, if file is not opened from 60 days, automatically move it to Cold Storage.

If it hasn't opened in a year then move it to Archive Storage. This moves Old data to cheaper pricing tiers automatically.

5.5 Scheduling and Auto Scaling :

Why pay for development server to run at 3:00 Am on Sunday if no developers are working ?

For environments that aren't live for customers you should use "Scheduling". Set up scripts that automatically turn off servers at 7:00 PM on Saturday and turn them on at 7:00 AM on Monday. This simple way can save upto 30% of the running costs for those servers.

For production environments use "Auto Scaling". This means cloud automatically adds more servers during busy times and removes them during quiet times. You only pay for power you need at that moment.

Applying the Methods:

1. Right-Sizing: We analyzed the CPU usage and realized that servers were only 10% busy. We switched them to medium-sized servers (50% cheaper).
2. Scheduling: We set up script to turn off the development servers at night (saving 30% of runtime).
3. Storage: We moved 300 GB of old logs to “Cold Storage” (saving roughly 40% on storage costs).

The Outcome: The calculation shows a significant drop in monthly bill:

- Original Bill: \$5,000 per month.
- Bill after Right-Sizing: \$2,500 per month.
- Bill after Scheduling & Storage changes: \$1,800 per month.

V. Tools for Managing Costs

You don't have to do this manually. The cloud Provider provides you free tools to help like:

- AWS: Provides “Cost Explorer” and “Trusted Advisor”. They analyze what you are running and give red flag to things which are wasting money.
- Azure: Provides “Azure Cost Management + Billing.”
- Google Cloud: Has “Billing reports” and “Cost table reports”.

These tools can set budgets and send you email alert if your bill is projected to go over a certain amount before the month ends.

VI. Results

To test the methods discussed till now, we apply a theoretical cost-optimization model to typical mid-sized startup scenario.

The Scenario: We imagine a company running a web application with the following setups:

- 10 large Virtual Servers running 24/7 (on-Demand Pricing).
- 500 GB of storage kept in “Hot-tier” (most expensive).
- No auto-scaling (servers run even at night when traffic is low).

Total Savings: By applying those simple methods, the total cost dropped by approximately 64%. This result proves that you do not need to rewrite your whole application code to save money, you just manage the infrastructure in better way and money will be saved.

VII. Conclusion

Cloud Computing is amazing technology but it requires little focus towards spend. The “pay-as-you-go” model is great for flexibility, but it is dangerous for your wallet if ignored.

Cost Optimization is a ongoing process of monitoring, analyzing and adjusting. It is not a one time process. By doing simple things like turning off unused machines, choosing right servers, committing to long-term plans for discounts, and managing storage servers, businesses and individuals can significantly cut their cloud bills. The goal is to Pay only for Value, not for waste.